

Carrier method for the general evaluation and control of pose, molecular conformation, tracking, and the like

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Abstract. The four basic geometric objects of points, point pairs, circles and spheres correspond to outer product null-spaces constructed by conformal points in conformal geometric algebra. Wedging with the infinity point we get four flat objects: finite-infinity point pairs, lines, planes and the whole 5D space. We show that all these basic geometric objects have the *same algebraic structure*. We then develop a single general algebraic method to quantify and interpolate the *relative pose* of the eight different classes of objects. As an explicit example we finally *apply* our framework to the conformation of organic macromolecules.

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1. Introduction

The relative pose of objects is based on geometric object definitions and the subsequent comparison of geometric features of these objects. Rigid motions in Euclidean spaces, that bring objects into identical positions and parallel orientation, need to be computed. Applying rescaling operations we can further match the size of objects.

We will define objects as blades in conformal geometric algebra [1, 2]. To introduce conformal geometric algebra [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8] we will briefly define the notions we use from Clifford geometric algebra [9, 10]. Excellent recent textbooks

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on conformal geometric algebra are [10, 11]. Our approach may be compared with [12, 13], yet we exclusively rely on algebraic methods, which are independent of the intrinsic object dimensions.

The four basic geometric objects of points, point pairs, circles and spheres correspond to outer product null-spaces of conformal points in conformal geometric algebra. All basic geometric objects have the same algebraic structure given by a minimal Euclidean blade (scalar, vector, bivector, trivector) called carrier, by their scalar radius and center. Wedging with the infinity point we get four flat objects: finite-infinity point pairs, lines, planes and the whole 5D space $\mathbb{R}^{4,1}$.

We state simple, but fully general, algebraic formulas to extract radii, and object specific (positioned and non-positioned) carriers. Quotients allow us to compute object position translators, relative translators, and relative rotors. The radii lead to rescaling operations. A very intuitive combination of these rotors, translators and rescaling finally yields fully general relative motors and matching operators which completely reveal the relative pose and extension of any two objects.

We thus develop a single general algebraic method to quantify and interpolate the relative pose of eight different classes of objects. We are absolutely free to begin with object points or higher order geometric algebra objects. Without extra effort the method can thus be adapted to whatever information is available.

Our method can be universally applied to the *conformation of molecules*, to human and robot pose problems, to the interpolation of motion, or to aerospace control and virtual reality problems, to name just a few.

Finally we demonstrate an application to biochemistry [14], where we further employ self-organizing maps (SOM) of Kohonen [15, 16] to evaluate the pose of methionin-enkephalin in solution from extensive molecular dynamics simulations. This is also a contribution to the growing field of Clifford algebra neural networks [17, 18]. The high dimensional conformation space is thus successfully reduced to a representative two-dimensional topology preserving map. This map provides a clear visual understanding of the solution environment dependent conformation changes of the bio-molecule.

1.1. Geometric algebra

Definition 1.1 (Clifford geometric algebra). A Clifford geometric algebra $\mathcal{G}_{p,q}$ is defined by the associative geometric product of elements of a quadratic vector space $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$, their linear combination and closure. $\mathcal{G}_{p,q}$ includes the field of real numbers \mathbb{R} and the vector space $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ as subspaces. The geometric product of two vectors is defined as

$$\mathbf{ab} = \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} + \mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{b}, \quad (1.1)$$

where $\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}$ indicates the standard inner product and the bivector $\mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{b}$ indicates Grassmann's antisymmetric outer product. $\mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{b}$ can be geometrically interpreted as the oriented parallelogram area spanned by the vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} . Geometric algebras are graded, with grades (subspace dimensions) ranging from zero (scalars) to $n = p + q$ (pseudoscalars, n -volumes).

The geometric algebra $\mathcal{G}_3 = \mathcal{G}_{3,0}$ of three-dimensional Euclidean space $\mathbb{R}^3 = \mathbb{R}^{3,0}$ has an eight-dimensional basis of scalars (grade 0), vectors (grade 1), bivectors (grade 2) and trivectors (grade 3). Trivectors in \mathcal{G}_3 are also referred to as oriented volumes or pseudoscalars. Using an orthonormal basis $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3\}$ for \mathbb{R}^3 we can write the basis of \mathcal{G}_3 as

$$\{1, \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3, \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_3, \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_2, i = \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_3\}. \quad (1.2)$$

In (1.2) i is the unit trivector, i.e. the oriented volume of a unit cube. Let us point out, that the even subalgebra \mathcal{G}_3^+ of \mathcal{G}_3 with basis

$$\{1, \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_3, \mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_2\} \quad (1.3)$$

is isomorphic to the quaternions \mathbb{H} of Hamilton. We therefore call elements of \mathcal{G}_3^+ rotors (shorthand for rotation operators), because they can be used to implement rotations of vectors (and all other elements) of \mathcal{G}_3 . The role of quaternion conjugation is naturally taken by reversion

$$(\mathbf{a}_1\mathbf{a}_2 \dots \mathbf{a}_s)^\sim = \mathbf{a}_s \dots \mathbf{a}_2\mathbf{a}_1, \quad \mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_s \in \mathbb{R}^{p,q}, \quad s \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (1.4)$$

The inverse of a non-*isotropic*¹ vector \mathbf{a} with respect to the geometric product is defined as

$$\mathbf{a}^{-1} = \frac{\mathbf{a}}{\mathbf{a}^2}. \quad (1.5)$$

A reflection at a hyperplane [20] with normal vector $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{x}' = -\mathbf{a}^{-1}\mathbf{x}\mathbf{a}. \quad (1.6)$$

In (1.6) the component of \mathbf{x} perpendicular to \mathbf{a} (i.e. the component parallel to the hyperplane) is preserved, while the direction of the component of \mathbf{x} parallel to \mathbf{a} (i.e. the component perpendicular to the hyperplane) is reversed.

A rotation by the angle θ in the plane of a unit bivector \mathbf{i} can thus be given as the product $R = \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b}$ of two vectors \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} from the \mathbf{i} -plane (i.e. geometrically as a sequence of two reflections) with angle $\theta/2$,

$$\mathbb{R}^{p,q} \ni \mathbf{x} \rightarrow R^{-1}\mathbf{x}R \in \mathbb{R}^{p,q}, \quad (1.7)$$

where the vectors \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} are in the plane of the unit bivector $\mathbf{i} \in \mathcal{G}_{p,q}$ if and only if $\mathbf{a} \wedge \mathbf{i} = \mathbf{b} \wedge \mathbf{i} = 0$. The rotor R can also be expanded as

$$R = \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b} = |\mathbf{a}||\mathbf{b}|\exp(\theta\mathbf{i}/2), \quad (1.8)$$

where $|\mathbf{a}|$, and $|\mathbf{b}|$ are the lengths of \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} . Please note that rotors are sometimes given as quotients of vectors, i.e.

$$R' = \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b}^{-1} = \frac{|\mathbf{a}|}{|\mathbf{b}|}\exp(\theta\mathbf{i}/2), \quad (1.9)$$

because in the bivector \mathbf{i} -plane we then have the obvious rotation relation

$$\mathbf{a} = R'\mathbf{b}. \quad (1.10)$$

¹An isotropic vector \mathbf{n} , also called null vector or light like vector in physics, squares to zero, i. e. $\mathbf{n}^2 = 0$.

Blades of grade k , $0 \leq k \leq n = p + q$ are the outer products of k vectors \mathbf{a}_l ($1 \leq l \leq k$) and directly represent the k -dimensional vector subspaces V spanned by the set of vectors \mathbf{a}_l ($1 \leq l \leq k$). This subspace representation is also called outer product null space (OPNS) representation.

$$\mathbf{x} \in V = \text{span}[\mathbf{a}_l, 1 \leq l \leq k] \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x} \wedge \mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \mathbf{a}_k = 0. \quad (1.11)$$

Extracting a certain grade part from the geometric product of two blades A_k and B_l has a deep geometric meaning.

For example the scalar (grade zero) part of the geometric product $A_k B_l$ is a form of generalization of the inner product of vectors to blades that results in a scalar, just as the inner product of vectors results in a scalar

$$A_k * B_l = \langle A_k B_l \rangle_0. \quad (1.12)$$

If $A_k * B_k = 0$ for non-*isotropic*² blades A_k and B_k of the same grade, then these blades are perpendicular to each other. The scalar product (1.12) is symmetric, like the inner product of vectors.

Another example is the grade $l - k$ part of the geometric product $A_k B_l$, that represents the orthogonal complement of A_k in B_l , provided that A_k is contained in B_l

$$A_k \lrcorner B_l = \langle A_k B_l \rangle_{l-k} \quad (1.13)$$

Because of its geometrical significance this grade part is called contraction [10] of A_k on B_l . The general elements of a geometric algebra are called multivectors. The contraction of two multivectors is defined as

$$A \lrcorner B = \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^n \langle A \rangle_k \right\} \lrcorner \left\{ \sum_{l=0}^n \langle B \rangle_l \right\} = \sum_{k,l=0}^n \langle \langle A \rangle_k \langle B \rangle_l \rangle_{l-k}, \quad (1.14)$$

where $\langle \langle A \rangle_k \langle B \rangle_l \rangle_{l-k} = 0$ for $l - k < 0$, because geometrically a vector space cannot be contained in one of its proper subspaces. There is an analogous definition of right contraction as (note the $k - l$ grade extraction!)

$$A \llcorner B = \sum_{k,l=0}^n \langle \langle A \rangle_k \langle B \rangle_l \rangle_{k-l}. \quad (1.15)$$

Yet another important grade part of the geometric product of A_k and B_l is the maximum grade $l + k$ part, also called the outer product part

$$A_k \wedge B_l = \langle A_k B_l \rangle_{l+k}. \quad (1.16)$$

If $A_k \wedge B_l$ is non-zero it represents the union of the disjoint (except for the zero vector) subspaces represented by A_k and B_l .

The contraction (1.13) offers the possibility to compute the complimentary subspace V^* in $\mathbb{R}^{q,p}$ of the direct OPNS subspace V represented by the blade A_k . $\mathbb{R}^{q,p}$ itself is directly OPNS represented by the unit pseudoscalar $I \in \mathcal{G}_{q,p}$ or

²An isotropic blade A_k , also called null blade, squares to zero, i. e. $A_k^2 = 0$.

equivalently by $I^{-1} = I/I^2$. V^* can thus be represented by the contraction of A_k on I^{-1}

$$A_k^* = A_k \lrcorner I^{-1} = A_k I^{-1}. \quad (1.17)$$

Up to a possible change of sign we have

$$(A_k^*)^* = \pm A_k. \quad (1.18)$$

The sign on the right side of (1.18) equals the sign of I^2 . That the complement of the union $A_k \wedge B_l$ of A_k and B_l in $\mathbb{R}^{q,p}$ equals the complement of A_k with respect to the complement of B_l in $\mathbb{R}^{q,p}$ (i.e. first removing the B_l dependence from $\mathbb{R}^{q,p}$ and then the A_k dependence from $\mathbb{R}^{q,p}$, see (1.13) and its interpretation) is algebraically expressed by the following identity

$$(A_k \wedge B_l)^* = A_k \lrcorner (B_l \lrcorner I^{-1}) = A_k \lrcorner B_l^*. \quad (1.19)$$

We can thus fully replace the direct OPNS definition of a subspace (1.11) by its standard inner product null space (IPNS) definition

$$\mathbf{x} \in V = \text{span}[\mathbf{a}_l, 0 \leq l \leq k] \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{x} \lrcorner (\mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \mathbf{a}_k)^* = 0, \quad (1.20)$$

because

$$(\mathbf{x} \wedge \mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \mathbf{a}_k)^* = \mathbf{x} \lrcorner (\mathbf{a}_1 \wedge \mathbf{a}_2 \wedge \dots \wedge \mathbf{a}_k)^* \quad (1.21)$$

Usually the OPNS subspace representation (1.11) and the IPNS subspace representation (1.20) are used dependent on the convenience of the resulting blade expressions. Examples of this alternative use will be encountered below, and has geometric significance beyond the mere algebraic manipulations of blade expressions.

The geometric algebras $\mathcal{G}_{p+1,q+1}$ are of special interest and are called conformal geometric algebras. One reason is that all orthogonal transformation groups $O(p, q)$ of vector spaces $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ are cases of Clifford (or Lipschitz) groups (defined below) of these spaces. Conformal transformation groups $C(p, q)$ preserve inner products (angles) of vectors in $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ up to a change of scale. Now the conformal group $C(p, q)$ is isomorphic to the orthogonal group $O(p+1, q+1)$. The metric affine group (consisting of orthogonal transformations and translations) of $\mathbb{R}^{p,q}$ is a special subgroup (specified below) of the orthogonal group $O(p+1, q+1)$, and can thus be implemented as a Clifford group in $\mathcal{G}_{p+1,q+1}$.

The different signs (parities) of (1.6) and (1.7), due to odd and even numbers of vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} can be generally taken care of by introducing the grade involution of multivectors $A \in \mathcal{G}_{p,q}$

$$\widehat{A} = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \langle A \rangle_k. \quad (1.22)$$

Now we can define [9] the powerful notion of Clifford (or Lipschitz) group which includes $\text{Pin}(p, q)$, $\text{Spin}(p, q)$, and $\text{Spin}_+(p, q)$ groups as covering groups of orthogonal $O(p, q)$, special orthogonal $SO(p, q)$ and $SO_+(p, q)$ groups, respectively. A

Clifford group is the subgroup in $\mathcal{G}_{p,q}$ generated by non-isotropic vectors $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{q,p}$ in the following way

$$\Gamma_{p,q} = \{m \in \mathcal{G}_{p,q} \mid \forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{q,p}, \widehat{m}^{-1} \mathbf{x} m \in \mathbb{R}^{q,p}\} \quad (1.23)$$

For every $m \in \Gamma_{p,q}$ we have $m\widehat{m} \in \mathbb{R}$. Further details are given in [4, 9, 19].

1.2. Conformal geometric algebra $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$

Given an orthonormal basis for $\mathbb{R}^{4,1}$

$$\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3, \mathbf{e}_+, \mathbf{e}_-\} \quad (1.24)$$

with

$$\mathbf{e}_1^2 = \mathbf{e}_2^2 = \mathbf{e}_3^2 = \mathbf{e}_+^2 = -\mathbf{e}_-^2 = 1, \quad (1.25)$$

we introduce a change of basis for the two additional dimensions $\{\mathbf{e}_+, \mathbf{e}_-\}$ by

$$\mathbf{e}_0 = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{e}_+ - \mathbf{e}_-), \quad \mathbf{e}_\infty = \mathbf{e}_+ + \mathbf{e}_-. \quad (1.26)$$

The vectors \mathbf{e}_0 and \mathbf{e}_∞ are *isotropic* vectors, i.e.

$$\mathbf{e}_0^2 = \mathbf{e}_\infty^2 = 0, \quad (1.27)$$

And have inner and outer products of

$$\mathbf{e}_0 \cdot \mathbf{e}_\infty = -1, \quad E = \mathbf{e}_\infty \wedge \mathbf{e}_0 = \mathbf{e}_+ \wedge \mathbf{e}_-. \quad (1.28)$$

We further have the following useful relationships

$$\mathbf{e}_0 E = -\mathbf{e}_0, \quad E \mathbf{e}_0 = \mathbf{e}_0, \quad \mathbf{e}_\infty E = \mathbf{e}_\infty, \quad E \mathbf{e}_\infty = -\mathbf{e}_\infty, \quad E^2 = 1. \quad (1.29)$$

Because E is an even grade bivector and orthogonal to all Euclidean vectors $\in \mathbb{R}^3$, it naturally commutes with every Euclidean vector (and hence with every Euclidean multivector).

2. Characterization of geometric objects in conformal geometric algebra

2.1. Points, point pairs, circles and spheres as general 0D, 1D, 2D and 3D spheres

Apart from the group theoretic reasons explained above, the conformal geometric algebra $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ provides us with a model of Euclidean geometry, which has a number of computational advantages. The basic geometric objects in conformal geometric algebra are homogeneous conformal points given by

$$P = \mathbf{p} + \frac{1}{2}p^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0, \quad (2.1)$$

where $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $p = \sqrt{\mathbf{p}^2}$. The $+\mathbf{e}_0$ term shows that we include projective geometry. The second term $+\frac{1}{2}p^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty$ ensures, that conformal points are isotropic vectors

$$P^2 = PP = P \cdot P = 0. \quad (2.2)$$

FIGURE 1. Conformal point pair, conformal circle and conformal sphere.

A point pair (Fig. 1) is conformally represented (in OPNS) by its outer product union

$$Pp = P_1 \wedge P_2 = 2r\{\mathbf{d} \wedge \mathbf{c} + \frac{1}{2}[(c^2 + r^2)\mathbf{d} - 2\mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{d}]\mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{d}\mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{d} \cdot \mathbf{c}E\}, \quad (2.3)$$

with the "radius" r defined as half the Euclidean point pair distance, \mathbf{d} the unit vector pointing from \mathbf{p}_2 to \mathbf{p}_1 , and \mathbf{c} the Euclidean midpoint (center) of the point pair:

$$2r = |\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{p}_2|, \quad \mathbf{d} = \frac{\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{p}_2}{2r}, \quad \mathbf{c} = \frac{\mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{p}_2}{2}, \quad c = |\mathbf{c}|. \quad (2.4)$$

The use of r , \mathbf{c} , and Euclidean carrier \mathbf{d} corresponds to interpreting a point pair as a sphere in one dimension. The Euclidean carrier \mathbf{d} provides an OPNS representation of the 1D straight line subspace of \mathbb{R}^3 parallel to the line containing the point pair. Using the left and right contractions (1.14) and (1.15) we can replace the inner products in (2.3) and get

$$Pp = 2r\{\mathbf{d} \wedge \mathbf{c} + \frac{1}{2}[(c^2 + r^2)\mathbf{d} - 2\mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{d}]\mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{d}\mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{d} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} E\}, \quad (2.5)$$

The conformal outer product null space spanned by three conformal points is a Euclidean sphere in 2D, i.e. a circle (Fig. 1)

$$Circle = P_1 \wedge P_2 \wedge P_3 = \mathbf{i}_c \wedge \mathbf{c} + [\frac{1}{2}(r^2 + c^2)\mathbf{i}_c - \mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{c} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{i}_c]\mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{i}_c \mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{i}_c \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} E \quad (2.6)$$

where r is the Euclidean radius, \mathbf{c} the Euclidean center and \mathbf{i}_c the Euclidean carrier plane parallel to the plane of the circle (2.6).

The conformal outer product null space spanned by four conformal points is a 3D Euclidean sphere (Fig. 1)

$$\begin{aligned} Sphere &= P_1 \wedge P_2 \wedge P_3 \wedge P_4 \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(r^2 - c^2)i_s \mathbf{e}_\infty + i_s \mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{c} i_s E \\ &= (\mathbf{c} + \frac{1}{2}c^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0 - \frac{1}{2}r^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty) i_s E \\ &= (C - \frac{1}{2}r^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty) i_s E, \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

where r is again the Euclidean radius, \mathbf{c} the Euclidean center and i_s a multiple of the Euclidean pseudoscalar i , which thus represents the Euclidean carrier space \mathbb{R}^3 , of the sphere. The following relations

$$i_s \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} = i_s \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c} i_s = \mathbf{c} \mathbf{J} i_s, \quad \mathbf{c} \wedge i_s = 0, \quad (2.8)$$

allow us to rewrite (2.7) in a form analogous to (2.5) and (2.6)

$$Sphere = i_s \wedge \mathbf{c} + \left[\frac{1}{2}(r^2 + c^2)i_s - \mathbf{c} \mathbf{c} \mathbf{J} i_s \right] \mathbf{e}_\infty + i_s \mathbf{e}_0 + i_s \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} E \quad (2.9)$$

We can regard a point (2.1) as a 0D point sphere with radius $r = 0$, center $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{p}$, and scalar Euclidean carrier 1. Taking into account that

$$1 \wedge \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}, \quad (2.10)$$

and that

$$\mathbf{c} \mathbf{J} 1 = 1 \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} = 0, \quad (2.11)$$

because the Euclidean 0D space 1 cannot contain a 1D vector \mathbf{c} , we can somewhat artificially rewrite (2.1) in analogy to (2.5), (2.6) and (2.9) as

$$P = \mathbf{c} + \frac{1}{2}c^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0 = 1 \wedge \mathbf{c} + \left[\frac{1}{2}(0^2 + c^2)1 - \mathbf{c} \mathbf{c} \mathbf{J} 1 \right] \mathbf{e}_\infty + 1 \mathbf{e}_0 + 1 \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} E. \quad (2.12)$$

Comparing (2.5), (2.6), (2.9) and (2.12) we make the interesting observation, that conformal points, point pairs, circles and spheres have an identical form, they are only distinguished by their respective scalar, vector, bivector and trivector Euclidean carriers

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{point } P \\ \mathbf{d}, & \text{point pair } Pp \\ \mathbf{i}_c, & \text{circle } Circle \\ i_s, & \text{sphere } Sphere \end{cases} \quad (2.13)$$

The general common form of the homogeneous conformal points, point pairs, circles and spheres (i.e. 0D, 1D, 2D, and 3D spheres) is therefore, using the carriers \mathbf{D} defined in (2.13),

$$S = \mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} + \left[\frac{1}{2}(c^2 + r^2)\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{c} \mathbf{c} \mathbf{J} \mathbf{D} \right] \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} E. \quad (2.14)$$

We emphasize that this common form is only possible by using both the left and the right contraction (1.14) and (1.15), respectively. The real scalar r universally expresses the radius extension, and \mathbf{c} the geometric center of each object.

Remark 2.1. The Euclidean carrier $\mathbf{D} \in \mathcal{G}^3 \subset \mathcal{G}^{4,1}$ is the OPNS subspace representation of the minimal (i.e. of lowest possible dimension) Euclidean subspace to include the whole geometric object when it is placed at the origin.

At the origin ($\mathbf{c} = 0$) all the geometric objects have the form

$$S_0 = \mathbf{D} \left(\frac{r^2}{2} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0 \right). \quad (2.15)$$

FIGURE 2. Conformal line and plane.

2.2. Flat objects of flat points, lines, planes and the 5D space $\mathbb{R}^{4,1}$

In the conformal representations of circles (2.6) and spheres (2.7) the point at infinity \mathbf{e}_∞ is not excluded. Indeed if one of the points is at infinity, we get conformal lines (Fig. 2) as flattened circles passing through infinity

$$\text{Line} = P_1 \wedge P_2 \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = 2r\mathbf{d} \wedge C \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = 2r\{\mathbf{d} \wedge \mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty - \mathbf{d}E\}, \quad (2.16)$$

and conformal planes (Fig. 2) as spheres passing through infinity

$$\text{Plane} = P_1 \wedge P_2 \wedge P_3 \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = \mathbf{i}_c \wedge C \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = \mathbf{i}_c \wedge \mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty - \mathbf{i}_c E \quad (2.17)$$

In (2.16) the vector \mathbf{d} is now the Euclidean direction vector of the line, which can also be interpreted as representing the Euclidean carrier of the 1D subspace of \mathbb{R}^3 parallel to the line (2.16). The moment bivector of the line is given as

$$\mathbf{d} \wedge \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{d}\mathbf{c}_\perp, \quad (2.18)$$

where \mathbf{c}_\perp is the Euclidean distance of the line (2.16) from the origin. Similarly the bivector \mathbf{i}_c in (2.17) represents the 2D Euclidean carrier subspace of \mathbb{R}^3 parallel to the plane (2.17). The moment trivector of the plane is given as

$$\mathbf{i}_c \wedge \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{i}_c \mathbf{c}_\perp, \quad (2.19)$$

where \mathbf{c}_\perp is the Euclidean distance of the plane (2.17) from the origin. Compare (Fig. 2).

Lines (planes) can thus be regarded as flattened circles (spheres) taking one point in (2.6) (and (2.7)) to infinity $P_3 \rightarrow \mathbf{e}_\infty$ ($P_4 \rightarrow \mathbf{e}_\infty$) or as directly generated by wedging a point pair (2.3) (and a circle (2.6)) with infinity \mathbf{e}_∞ .

$$\text{Line} = Pp \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty, \quad (2.20)$$

$$\text{Plane} = \text{Circle} \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty. \quad (2.21)$$

The second viewpoint clearly shows the intimate relationship of point pairs with lines (circles with planes). In a sense all geometric properties of a line (plane) are already encoded in the wedge product of two (three) conformal points of the line (plane).

Consequently one can further introduce two more flattened objects,

$$P \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty, \quad (2.22)$$

a (flat) finite–infinite point pair, and

$$-i_s E = Sphere \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty, \quad (2.23)$$

a 5D pseudoscalar proportional to the 5D unit pseudoscalar $I = iE$ representing the (flat) 5D conformal space $\mathbb{R}^{4,1}$, i.e. the embedded (flat) 3D Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 .

We consequently observe that all four flat objects, i.e. finite–infinite point pair, line, plane and the (embedded) 3D space \mathbb{R}^3 itself have one common form, based on wedging the general sphere S of (2.14) with the point at infinity \mathbf{e}_∞

$$F = S \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = \mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty - \mathbf{D} E = \mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty - \mathbf{D} E, \quad (2.24)$$

where \mathbf{D} is the respective Euclidean carrier (2.13), and

$$\mathbf{c}_\perp = \begin{cases} \mathbf{p}, & \text{finite–infinite point pair} \\ \mathbf{c}_\perp, & \text{line } Line \\ \mathbf{c}_\perp, & \text{plane } Plane \\ 0, & \text{3D space } \mathbb{R}^3 \end{cases} \quad (2.25)$$

the Euclidean distance vector from the origin. The geometric information contained in $[\frac{1}{2}(c^2 + r^2)\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{c} \mathbf{c} \lrcorner \mathbf{D}]$ and $\mathbf{D} \lrcorner \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\parallel$ of radius r and object center vector component \mathbf{c}_\parallel parallel to \mathbf{D} is thus naturally deleted, it makes no sense for the flat object. The algebraic reason is, that

$$\mathbf{e}_\infty \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = 0, \text{ and } E \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = \mathbf{e}_\infty \wedge \mathbf{e}_0 \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = 0. \quad (2.26)$$

Remark 2.2. Placing a flat object at the origin ($\mathbf{c}_\perp = 0$) naturally yields

$$F_0 = S_0 \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = -\mathbf{D} E, \quad (2.27)$$

i.e. the carrier \mathbf{D} itself embedded (factor $-E$) in the 5D space $\mathbb{R}^{4,1}$. In [10] the notion of carrier is defined by $F = S \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty$ of (2.24). Equation (2.27) shows how these two definitions are related.

2.3. Computing carrier, radius and position information

A very important result about the general algebraic computation of the carrier \mathbf{D} is stated in the following theorem.

Theorem 2.3 (Carrier computation). *The carrier \mathbf{D} of any type of sphere S of (2.14), and of any type of flat object F of (2.24) can be computed by*

$$\mathbf{D} = -(S \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty) \lrcorner E = -F \lrcorner E. \quad (2.28)$$

Remark 2.1 about the carrier \mathbf{D} applies both to spheres S and flat objects F . Formula (2.28) is fully position independent, i.e. independent of \mathbf{c} and \mathbf{c}_\perp . We now proof theorem 2.3.

Proof. With (2.24) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
(S \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty) \mathbf{L} E &= (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty - \mathbf{D} E) \mathbf{L} E \\
&= (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty) \mathbf{L} E - (\mathbf{D} E) \mathbf{L} E \\
&= \langle \mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty E \rangle_{(k_s+1-2)} - \langle \mathbf{D} E E \rangle_{(k_s+1-2)} \\
&= \langle \mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty \rangle_{(k_s-1)} - \langle \mathbf{D} \rangle_{(k_s-1)} \\
&= 0 - \mathbf{D} = -\mathbf{D}.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.29}$$

In (2.29) $k_s = 1, 2, 3, 4$ is the grade of the conformal sphere S , which corresponds in the OPNS to the number k_s of conformal points P_j , $1 \leq j \leq k_s$ used to construct S in (2.12), (2.5), (2.6), and (2.9), respectively. We observe from (2.13) that the grade of the Euclidean carrier \mathbf{D} is $k_s - 1$. Therefore the grade of $\mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp$ is $k_s - 1 + 1 = k_s$ and the grade of $\mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty = \mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty$ is $k_s + 1$.

For the third equality of (2.29) we used the definition of the right contraction (1.15), and the fact that $\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty$ and $\mathbf{D} E$ are blades of grade $k_s + 1$, and that E is a bivector of grade 2. For the fourth equality of (2.29) we used the conformal algebra relationships (1.29). For the fifth equality of (2.29) we used that the blade $\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty$ of grade $k_s + 1$ has no grade $k_s - 1$ part, and that the grade of \mathbf{D} is exactly $k_s - 1$. \square

We can immediately apply (2.28) in order to obtain the following result.

Theorem 2.4 (Radius computation). *The radius r of a general sphere S of (2.14) can be computed by*

$$r^2 = \frac{S\widehat{S}}{\mathbf{D}^2}. \tag{2.30}$$

Proof. We state the proof only for objects at the origin ($\mathbf{c} = 0$). Using the translators of the next section to translate an object to $\mathbf{c} \neq 0$ would not change the result because both the numerator $S\widehat{S} = S * \widehat{S}$ and the denominator $D^2 = D * D$ are translation invariant scalars. Assuming $\mathbf{c} = 0$ we get from (2.14) that

$$\begin{aligned}
S\widehat{S} &= (-1)^{k_s} \left(\frac{r^2}{2} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 \right) * \left(\frac{r^2}{2} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 \right) \\
&= (-1)^{k_s} \left\langle \frac{r^4}{4} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 \right\rangle_0 + 2(-1)^{k_s} \left\langle \frac{r^2}{2} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 \right\rangle_0 \\
&= 2(-1)^{k_s} \frac{r^2}{2} \langle \mathbf{D} \mathbf{D} (-1)^{k_s-1} \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{e}_0 \rangle_0 \\
&= -r^2 \mathbf{D}^2 \langle \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{e}_0 \rangle_0 = -r^2 \mathbf{D}^2 (-1) = r^2 \mathbf{D}^2.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.31}$$

For the second equality of (2.31) we used the definition and the symmetry of the scalar product (1.12). For the third equality we used that both \mathbf{e}_0 and \mathbf{e}_∞ square to zero, and that \mathbf{D} is of grade $k_s - 1$. This produces the sign in the commutation $\mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} = (-1)^{k_s-1} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_\infty$. For the fourth equality we used (1.28). \square

Remark 2.5. Alternative to (2.30), the formula $r^2 = S^2 / (S \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty)^2$ is given in [10], section 14.1.2.

We establish the following theorem, regarding the Euclidean center \mathbf{c} of a general object S of (2.14), or the Euclidean distance vector \mathbf{c}_\perp of a flat object F of (2.24) from the origin.

Theorem 2.6 (Center computation). *The position of a general object is given by its center vector $\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}_\parallel + \mathbf{c}_\perp$, the position of a flat object is given by its perpendicular (to the carrier \mathbf{D}) distance vector \mathbf{c}_\perp from the origin. The Euclidean center vector components \mathbf{c}_\parallel (parallel to the carrier \mathbf{D}) and \mathbf{c}_\perp can now be computed by*

$$\mathbf{c}_\parallel = \mathbf{D}^{-1}(S \llcorner E), \quad \mathbf{c}_\perp = \mathbf{D}^{-1}(S \wedge E)E = \mathbf{D}^{-1}(F \wedge \mathbf{e}_0)E \quad (2.32)$$

or together for general objects S in one formula as

$$\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{D}^{-1}[S \wedge (1 + E)] \llcorner E. \quad (2.33)$$

Proof. Direct calculation based on (2.14) gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{D}^{-1}(S \llcorner E) \\ &= \mathbf{D}^{-1}(\mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} + [\frac{1}{2}(c^2 + r^2)\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{c} \mathbf{c} \llcorner \mathbf{D}]\mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{D} \llcorner \mathbf{c} E) \llcorner E \\ &= \mathbf{D}^{-1}\mathbf{D} \llcorner \mathbf{c} EE = \mathbf{D}^{-1}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{c}_\parallel = \mathbf{c}_\parallel, \end{aligned} \quad (2.34)$$

where we used

$$m \llcorner E = (m\mathbf{e}_0) \llcorner E = (m\mathbf{e}_\infty) \llcorner E = 0 \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{G}_{3,0} \subset \mathcal{G}_{4,1}, \quad (2.35)$$

(1.29), and that

$$\mathbf{D} \llcorner \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{c}_\parallel. \quad (2.36)$$

The perpendicular component \mathbf{c}_\perp can also be directly calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{D}^{-1}\{S \wedge E\}E \\ &= \mathbf{D}^{-1}\{(\mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} + [\frac{1}{2}(c^2 + r^2)\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{c} \mathbf{c} \llcorner \mathbf{D}]\mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{D} \llcorner \mathbf{c} E) \wedge E\}E \\ &= \mathbf{D}^{-1}\mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} EE = \mathbf{D}^{-1}\mathbf{D}\mathbf{c}_\perp = \mathbf{c}_\perp, \end{aligned} \quad (2.37)$$

where we used

$$(mE) \wedge E = (m\mathbf{e}_0) \wedge E = (m\mathbf{e}_\infty) \wedge E = 0 \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{G}_{3,0} \subset \mathcal{G}_{4,1}, \quad (2.38)$$

(1.29), and that

$$\mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{c}_\perp. \quad (2.39)$$

The second expression for \mathbf{c}_\perp in (2.32) uses the fact that

$$S \wedge E = S \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty \wedge \mathbf{e}_0 = F \wedge \mathbf{e}_0. \quad (2.40)$$

Equation (2.33) follows from

$$S \wedge 1 = S \quad \text{and} \quad (S \wedge E) \llcorner E = (S \wedge E)E. \quad (2.41)$$

□

Remark 2.7. Alternative to (2.33), a single product formula (with numerator quadratic in S) for the conformal center point is given in [10], section 16.2.1.

Before extracting more information from S or F , we briefly introduce motion operators in the conformal algebra $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$.

2.4. Motion operators (motors)

As in \mathcal{G}_3 , 3D rotations around the origin in the conformal model $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$ are still represented by rotors (1.7). The standard IPNS representation of a conformal plane, i.e. the dual of the direct OPNS representation (2.17) results in a vector, that both describes the unit normal direction $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{c}_\perp / |\mathbf{c}_\perp|$ and the position (signed distance $d = \mathbf{c}_\perp \cdot \mathbf{n}$ from the origin) of a plane by

$$\mu = \text{Plane}^* = \mathbf{n} + d\mathbf{e}_\infty. \quad (2.42)$$

We can reflect the conformal point X at the plane (2.42) similar to (1.6) with

$$X' = -\mu^{-1}X\mu. \quad (2.43)$$

Just as we obtained rotations (1.7) by double reflections we now obtain rotations around arbitrary axis (lines of intersection of two planes) by double reflections at planes μ_1 and μ_2

$$X' = R^{-1}XR, \quad R = \mu_1\mu_2. \quad (2.44)$$

And if the two planes μ_1 and μ_2 happen to be parallel, i.e. $\mathbf{n}_1 = \pm\mathbf{n}_2$, we instead get a translation by twice the Euclidean distance $\mathbf{t}/2$ between the planes

$$X' = T^{-1}XT, \quad T(\mathbf{t}) = \mu_1\mu_2 = 1 + \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{t}\mathbf{e}_\infty = \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{t}\mathbf{e}_\infty\right). \quad (2.45)$$

A general motion operator (motor) results from combining rotations (2.44) and translations (2.45) to

$$M = TR. \quad (2.46)$$

The standard IPNS representation of a sphere results in the vector

$$\sigma = C - \frac{1}{2}r^2\mathbf{e}_\infty, \quad (2.47)$$

which is exactly the dual of (2.7). The double reflection at two concentric spheres σ_1 and σ_2 (centered at \mathbf{c}) results in a rescaling operation [10] with factor s and center \mathbf{c}

$$X' = Z^{-1}XZ, \quad Z = \sigma_1\sigma_2 = T^{-1}(\mathbf{c}) \exp\left(E \frac{1}{2} \log s\right) T(\mathbf{c}). \quad (2.48)$$

2.5. The positioned carrier

Theorem 2.8 (Positioned carrier of general objects). *A positioned minimal Euclidean blade \mathbf{D}_T , that is uniquely related to the orientation and position of a conformal geometric object can be obtained for conformal points, point pairs, circles and spheres by*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_T &= (\mathbf{e}_\infty \widehat{S}) \wedge (1 + E) \\ &= \mathbf{D}(1 + \mathbf{c}\mathbf{e}_\infty) = \mathbf{D} \exp(\mathbf{c}\mathbf{e}_\infty). \end{aligned} \quad (2.49)$$

The reasons for calling \mathbf{D}_T *positioned* carrier are its relations with the (Euclidean) carrier \mathbf{D} of (2.13) and (2.28), and with the object center \mathbf{c} . Evidently we have with (2.45) that

$$\mathbf{D}_T = \mathbf{D}T(2\mathbf{c}) = \mathbf{D}T^2(\mathbf{c}). \quad (2.50)$$

Proof. We now proof (2.49) of theorem 2.8. The multiplication of a general spheres S (2.14) by \mathbf{e}_∞ results in

$$\mathbf{e}_\infty S = \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{e}_\infty \left[\frac{1}{2}(c^2 + r^2) \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{c} \mathbf{c} \lrcorner \mathbf{D} \right] \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{E} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} \quad (2.51)$$

The second term in (2.51) vanishes because $\mathbf{e}_\infty^2 = 0$. Using $\mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{e}_\infty$ of (1.29) we thus get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_\infty S &= \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 + \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} \\ &= \mathbf{e}_\infty (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{D} \wedge \mathbf{c}) + \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 = \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_0 \\ &= (-1)^{k_s-1} (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{e}_0) \\ &= (-1)^{k_s-1} (-\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D}(-1 + E)) \\ &= (-1)^{k_s} (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{D} E) \end{aligned} \quad (2.52)$$

For the third equality of (2.52) we used $\mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{D} = (-1)^{k_s-1} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{e}_\infty$. For the fourth equality we used $\mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty = -\mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{c}$, and $\mathbf{e}_\infty \mathbf{e}_0 = -1 + E$. Finally we calculate

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{e}_\infty S) \wedge (1 + E) &= (-1)^{k_s} (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{D} E) \wedge (1 + E) \\ &= (-1)^{k_s} (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{D} E + \mathbf{D} E) \\ &= (-1)^{k_s} \mathbf{D} (1 + \mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty) \end{aligned} \quad (2.53)$$

For the second equality of (2.53) we used $A \wedge 1 = A, \forall A \in \mathcal{G}_{4,1}$, $\mathbf{e}_\infty \wedge E = 0$, $E \wedge E = 0$ and $\mathbf{D} \wedge E = \mathbf{D} E$. Because $\widehat{S} = (-1)^{k_s}$ the factor $(-1)^{k_s}$ of (2.53) finally cancels out. \square

For flat objects F we establish the following related theorem.

Theorem 2.9 (Positioned carrier of flat objects). *The object specific positioned minimal Euclidean blade \mathbf{D}_T for flat objects like flat point pairs (i.e. finite-infinite point pairs), lines, planes, and the embedded three-dimensional space \mathbb{R}^3 , is obtained much simpler by*

$$\mathbf{D}_T = -EF = \mathbf{D}(1 + \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty) = \mathbf{D} \exp(\mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty). \quad (2.54)$$

Similar to (2.50) we now obviously have with (2.45) that

$$\mathbf{D}_T = \mathbf{D}T^2(\mathbf{c}_\perp). \quad (2.55)$$

Proof. We now proof (2.54). With (2.24) we get

$$\begin{aligned} -EF &= -E(\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty - \mathbf{D} E) = \mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp (-E \mathbf{e}_\infty) + \mathbf{D} E E \\ &= \mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{D} = \mathbf{D}(1 + \mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty). \end{aligned} \quad (2.56)$$

For the second equality of (2.56) we used the commutation property of E with the Euclidean blades \mathbf{D} and $\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}_\perp$ and the relations (1.29). \square

FIGURE 3. Relative pose and extension of point pairs $S_1 = P_1 \wedge P_2$ and $S_2 = Q_1 \wedge Q_2$. Scaling Z_1 , rotation R_1 , translation T , motion M , and motion-scaling M_s as explained in the text. Overbars for inverse operators: $\bar{Z}_1 = Z_1^{-1}$, etc.

Using the carriers \mathbf{D} and the positioned carriers \mathbf{D}_T , we can easily and fully general calculate the squares of the positioning translators by left division of (2.50) and (2.55) with \mathbf{D} as

$$T^2(\mathbf{c}) = \mathbf{D}^{-1} \mathbf{D}_T = \exp(\mathbf{c} \mathbf{e}_\infty), \quad (2.57)$$

and

$$T^2(\mathbf{c}_\perp) = \mathbf{D}^{-1} \mathbf{D}_T = \exp(\mathbf{c}_\perp \mathbf{e}_\infty), \quad (2.58)$$

respectively.

3. Relative measurements and relative pose

For all general spheres S and flat objects F we can now determine relative displacements and angles in the immediately applicable form of relative translators and relative rotors. For the general spheres S we can further calculate relative dilation operators.

From two carriers \mathbf{D}_1 and \mathbf{D}_2 of the same grade, we get the relative rotor R

$$R^2 = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \mathbf{D}_2 = F_{01}^{-1} F_{02} = (S_{01} \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty)^{-1} (S_{02} \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty). \quad (3.1)$$

The second equality in (3.1) with $F_0 = S_0 \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty$ of (2.27) follows from

$$F_{01}^{-1} F_{02} = (-E \mathbf{D}_1)^{-1} (-E \mathbf{D}_2) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} E^{-1} E \mathbf{D}_2 = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \mathbf{D}_2. \quad (3.2)$$

The embedded carrier F_0 of (2.27) allows therefore the direct computation of the relative rotor, which may be faster to compute in applications. For carriers of different grade (e.g. as in Fig. 4), equation (3.2) does obviously not apply. We therefore establish the following general relative rotation theorem.

FIGURE 4. Relative pose and extension of point pair $S_1 = P_1 \wedge P_2$ and circle S_2 . Transformations as explained in the text [rotation R_1 of (A3)].

FIGURE 5. Relative pose of circle S with center C , and plane F . Transformations as explained in the text.

Theorem 3.1 (General relative rotation). *We assume two general Euclidean blades \mathbf{D}_1 with grade g_1 and \mathbf{D}_2 with grade g_2 . The relative rotor $R(\theta)$ that rotates blade \mathbf{D}_2 into blade \mathbf{D}_1 can be computed as*

$$R^2(\theta) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1}(\mathbf{D}_1 \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_2^{-1} + \mathbf{D}_1 \llcorner \mathbf{D}_2^{-1})\mathbf{D}_2 + \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} * \mathbf{D}_2 + \langle \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \times \mathbf{D}_2 \rangle_{\text{even}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where \lrcorner and \llcorner specify the left and right contraction, respectively, $*$ the scalar product, \times the commutator product, and $\langle \dots \rangle_{\text{even}}$ extracts the even grade part of the enclosed multivector. Equation (3.3) returns zero if and only if both $\mathbf{D}_1 \perp \mathbf{D}_2$ and $g_1 \neq g_2$.

Remark 3.2. The detailed proof of theorem 3.1 is interesting, but lengthy. It is therefore given in appendix A. Using the dot product definition of appendix B.1.1

of [10], we can simplify (3.3) to

$$R^2(\theta) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1}(\mathbf{D}_1 \cdot \mathbf{D}_2^{-1})\mathbf{D}_2 + \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} * \mathbf{D}_2 + \langle \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \times \mathbf{D}_2 \rangle_{\text{even}}. \quad (3.4)$$

Equation (3.3) returns zero if and only if both $\mathbf{D}_1 \perp \mathbf{D}_2$ and $g_1 \neq g_2$. This means geometrically that the relative rotation between \mathbf{D}_1 and \mathbf{D}_2 is not unique. The relative angle $\theta = \pi/2$ is well defined, but the plane of rotation is not unique. For example for $\mathbf{D}_1 = \mathbf{e}_1$ and $\mathbf{D}_2 = \mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_3$ all planes with bivectors $\mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{v}$, $\mathbf{v} \in \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid \mathbf{x} \wedge \mathbf{D}_2 = 0\}$ can equally serve as rotation planes.

The general relative rotor R of (3.3) can rotate the first object (around its center \mathbf{c}_1), such that it becomes parallel to the second object

$$R_1^{-1} \text{Object}_1 R_1 \parallel \text{Object}_2, \quad R_1 = T_1^{-1} R T_1, \quad (3.5)$$

where $T_1 = T(\mathbf{c}_1)$ is obtained from (2.57), and the objects Object_1 and Object_2 can be *any* general sphere or flat object (Figs. 3, 4, 5). In particular the rotation of e.g. a circle parallel to a plane is thus also possible (Fig. 5), etc.

From the positioning translators T_1 , $T_2 = T(\mathbf{c}_2)$ of (2.57) and (2.58) we can compute relative translators

$$T = T_1^{-1} T_2, \quad (3.6)$$

which can translate any general sphere S_1 to the center of any other general sphere S_2 , irrespective of the dimensions (0D, 1D, 2D, 3D) of the spheres (and they don't need to have the same dimensions, compare Figs. 3, 4). With T of (3.6) we can also translate all general objects S to new positions in which their centers intersect with any flat object F (Fig. 5), again irrespective of the dimensions. Equation (3.6) also allows to translate two flat objects so that they coincide.

$$T^{-1} \text{Object}_1 T \text{ centrally intersects } \text{Object}_2. \quad (3.7)$$

If we further combine relative translators (3.6) with relative rotors (3.1) or (A3) we get relative motors

$$M = R_1 T = (T_1^{-1} R T_1) T_1^{-1} T_2 = T_1^{-1} R T_2, \quad (3.8)$$

which both redirect and reposition objects to become parallel and concentric. That means general spheres become concentric (Figs. 3, 4), and general spheres and flat objects become coincident, i.e. the flat object F will contain the general sphere S (Fig. 5), or $S \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty$ will contain F . For two flat objects the motor M has the effect of translating and rotating one object into the other, i.e. equal grade flat objects become identical, or the higher grade object fully contains the lower grade object.

With the help of the radius information (2.30) and the scaling operator (2.48)

$$Z_1 = T_1^{-1} Z_0(s) T_1, \quad Z_0(s) = \exp(E \frac{1}{2} \log s), \quad s = \frac{r_2}{r_1}. \quad (3.9)$$

we can finally rescale general spheres with finite radii r_1, r_2 , such that they end up having identical radii (motion-scaling, Figs. 3)

$$M_s = Z_1 M = T_1^{-1} Z_0(s) T_1^{-1} T_1 R T_2 = T_1^{-1} Z_0(s) R T_2. \quad (3.10)$$

This is also possible for spheres of different dimension (Fig. 4), i.e. for a point pair and a 3D sphere (then $R = 1$), etc.

For evaluation purposes the relative position, the plane \mathbf{i} , and the relative angle, of the relative rotation can easily be extracted from (3.6) and (3.1) or (A3), respectively, as

$$\mathbf{c}_2 - \mathbf{c}_1 = -2 T \mathbf{L} \mathbf{e}_0, \quad \mathbf{i} = \frac{\langle R \rangle_2}{|\langle R \rangle_2|}, \quad \theta = 2 \arctan\left(\frac{\langle R \rangle_2}{\mathbf{i} \langle R \rangle_0}\right). \quad (3.11)$$

Naturally (2.32) and (2.33) can also be used to calculate relative positions. The relative rotor R , the translators T_1, T_2 (and the scaling parameter s) thus completely reveal the relative pose (and extension) of two objects.

We have thus developed a general purely constructive algebraic method to quantify relative pose. We are free to begin with object points or higher order algebraic objects formed by outer products of points. The same method works for 0D, 1D, 2D and 3D Euclidean objects, between objects of different grade, and between general spherical and flat objects. Without extra effort the method can thus be adapted to whatever information is available.

Our method can be universally applied to evaluate the *conformation of molecules*, to solve human and robot pose problems, to the interpolation of motion, or to aerospace control and virtual reality problems. The next section gives an explicit example from biochemistry.

4. An application in computational biochemistry

This section describes an application of the above method to conformation analysis of a peptide, which is important in computational biochemistry. The details of the machine learning methodology are given in [14].

4.1. Background

Peptides are short polymers formed from the linkage of amino acids. Because of the flexibility of their structure, peptides show complicated dynamics and take various conformations in aqueous solution. Furthermore, the external conditions, such as temperature or concentration of other solvent components, significantly alter their structural properties. The dominant conformations and the transitions between them are very important for understanding the biological activity of a selected peptide when it functions as bioactive molecule. However, it is difficult to effectively classify the large number of different conformations of a peptide in solution. It is further difficult to comprehend the distribution of each conformation and the transition pathways between different conformations.

To overcome these problems, in the present study, we show the application of the above derived carrier method to the analysis of large numbers of different conformations of a peptide derived from a molecular dynamics (MD) simulation. We use methionine-enkephalin (M-Enk), which is composed of five amino acids (Tyr-Gly-Gly-Phe-Met) and contains 75 atoms, as a target molecule.

FIGURE 6. Molecular structure of methionin-enkephalin (M-Enk) and the 7 fragments (dotted circles) utilized to describe the conformation of M-Enk.

4.2. Methods

MD simulations produce the time histories of the three-dimensional Euclidean coordinates of all atoms in the system. However, it is computationally a very hard task to use all Euclidean coordinates of the constituent atoms of a peptide in the analysis due to the large degree of freedom. In addition, in computational biochemistry, internal coordinates are usually more useful to describe the conformational changes of a molecule.

In this work, to efficiently describe the conformation of our target peptide, we choose a number of fragments (atom groups) in the molecule (e.g. as in Fig. 6). The three dimensional Euclidean position vector of the j -th atom of the k -th fragment in the peptide at time t is denoted as $\mathbf{p}_{kj}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $k \in M$, $j \in N(k)$, where M is the number of fragments in the target peptide, $N(k)$ is the number of constituent atoms in the fragment k .

In the geometric algebra \mathcal{G}_3 , the relative orientation between two fragments k and k' at time t is evaluated as shown in eqs. (4.1) to (4.3). The k' can for instance be chosen as the adjacent fragment of i .

$$\frac{\mathbf{p}_{k1}(t) - \mathbf{p}_{k2}(t)}{\mathbf{p}_{k'1}(t) - \mathbf{p}_{k'2}(t)} = R^2(\vartheta_1) = R_1^2, \quad (4.1)$$

Equation (4.1) arises from (1.9), if we take into account that the vectors $\mathbf{p}_{k1}(t) - \mathbf{p}_{k2}(t)$ and $\mathbf{p}_{k'1}(t) - \mathbf{p}_{k'2}(t)$ enclose the full angle ϑ_1 and not $\vartheta_1/2$. For the parallel alignment of the chosen fragments k and k' , we further need to rotate with the

rotor R_2 given by

$$\frac{R_1^{-1}(\mathbf{p}_{k1}(t) - \mathbf{p}_{k3}(t))R_1}{\mathbf{p}_{k'1}(t) - \mathbf{p}_{k'3}(t)} = R_2^2, \quad (4.2)$$

The relative orientation of k and k' is therefore given by

$$R(t; k) = R_1 R_2. \quad (4.3)$$

The peptide shape at time t is evaluated with a series of m rotors as

$$x_t = [R(t; k) \mid k \in \{1, \dots, m\}]. \quad (4.4)$$

We can also use the conformal model of Euclidean space in $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$. We denote the line through the atoms j and j' of the fragment k according to (2.16) as $L_{k,jj'} = P_{kj} \wedge P_{kj'} \wedge \mathbf{e}_\infty$. Using (2.28) and (3.1) we can describe the relative orientation by eq. (4.3) with the following two rotors

$$R_1^2 = \frac{L_{k,12} \mathbf{L} E}{L_{k',12} \mathbf{L} E}, \quad (4.5)$$

$$R_2^2 = \frac{(R_1^{-1} L_{k,13} R_1) \mathbf{L} E}{L_{k',13} \mathbf{L} E}. \quad (4.6)$$

A mapping $f_\theta: V \rightarrow Y$ is self-organized by Kohonen's Self-Organizing Map (SOM) [15] when a distance space (V, d) is defined as, for example, $d: V^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$; $(x_t, x_{t'}) \mapsto \sum_k \|R(t; k) - R(t'; k)\|$, and a set of samples $X = \{x_t\} \subset V$ is given. Y is a visible space with $\dim Y \leq 2$. An efficient algorithm for cases like the M-Enk peptide MD simulations, where the number of samples $|X|$ is large, is proposed [16]. The SOM adjusts the parameters θ of the mapping $X \mapsto Y$, so that the topology of V , observed by X , is preserved in the visible space Y . The obtained mapping f_θ enables us to visualize in Y the trajectory of a simulated motion $[\dots, x_t \in V, \dots]$ in a selected solvent environment.

4.3. Results

To model the conformation of M-Enk, we choose a set M of 7 fragments (Fig. 6). Then, the peptide conformation at time t is described with a series of 6 rotors between adjacent fragments using the fragment 1 as a root.

Figure 7 shows the SOM of 10000 different conformations of M-Enk derived from the MD simulation. Each conformation is classified into its best match hexagonal cell, which stores the reference conformation. The gray level of the cells linearly corresponds to the end-to-end distance of the M-Enk peptide (i.e. darker gray tones of cells indicate the more extended conformations of M-Enk). The black solid line on the SOM shows the trajectory of the conformation change of M-Enk during a part of the MD simulation with a time duration of 1.0 nano-seconds. The analysis enables one to visually understand the pathway of the conformation change of M-Enk.

Furthermore, on the SOM, we depict the probability (i.e., frequency of appearance) for each M-Enk conformation sampled from the MD simulation in pure water at difference temperatures (Fig. 8). In each solvent environment, the relative

FIGURE 7. SOM of 10000 different conformations of M-Enk derived from the MD simulation. The trajectory of the conformation change of M-Enk (black solid line) during a part of the MD simulation with the time duration of 1.0 nano-seconds is superimposed on the SOM. Two typical reference conformations of M-Enk (backbone: red tube, side chains: blue lines) are depicted at both sides of the SOM.

size (radius) of the black circles linearly corresponds to the number of M-Enk conformations classified into each cell. This analysis shows how the high temperature (370K) aqueous environment delocalizes the distribution of M-Enk conformations observed at the room temperature (300K).

As demonstrated by this application, the combined use of geometric algebra and the SOM algorithm has great potential to gain an intuitive understanding of the structural and dynamical properties of flexible bio-macromolecules.

5. Conclusions

In this research we used the conformal model of three-dimensional Euclidean geometry in the conformal geometric algebra $\mathcal{G}_{4,1}$. The conformal model has two related classes of altogether eight geometric objects: four general spheres S of intrinsic dimensions zero (points), one (point pairs), two (circles) and three (spheres). The other class are the four flat objects F of finite-infinite point pair, line, plane and the fully embedded three-dimensional Euclidean space. The outer products of one, two, three and four conformal points fully define the spheres S , and the outer products of each S with the infinity vector define the related flat objects F .

We have derived general expressions for the spheres S and the flat objects F , only distinguished by the corresponding scalar, vector, bivector and trivector Euclidean *carriers*. The carrier specifies a minimal Euclidean subspace parallel to the object, which includes the object, after parallel transporting it to the origin.

FIGURE 8. Probability (black filled circles on the hexagonal cell) for each M-Enk conformation in pure water at temperature 300K (left) and at 370K (right).

We further derived general formulas to compute the carriers, the position, and (for spheres S) the radius of all objects. We then introduced the positioned carrier (Euclidean carrier times the square of the object position translator) and general formulas for its computation.

This algebraic toolset allows us finally to generally compute relative rotors, relative translators, and (for spheres S) rescaling operations. These algebraic operators can be applied to all objects for parallel reorientation, concentric (or intersecting) repositioning, and (for spheres S) rescaling to identical sizes. The relative position, relative orientation and relative extension are easily computed explicitly.

We have thus created a very general framework for processing and fully evaluating geometric object information and for investigating relative geometric properties of objects. The results include a full set of explicit geometric algebra operators for pose and extension. We demonstrated the utility of our approach with an explicit example from computational biochemistry. In this example we were able to gain an intuitive understanding of the structural and dynamical properties of a flexible bio-macromolecule.

Geometric algebra offers a new comprehensive framework for geometric problems in computer science [10, 17, 12]. We expect our results to find many applications in diverse fields, e.g. in aerospace engineering, robotics, computer graphics, image processing, motion tracking, artificial intelligence, virtual reality, advanced neural networks, computational biochemistry, nano-mechanics, etc.

Future research may extend our methods from three-dimensional to n -dimensional space. Other research options could be multivector data distributions, independent component analysis in the framework of geometric algebra, and the extension of our techniques to differential multivector geometry.

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Appendix A. Proof of theorem 3.1

We now proof theorem 3.1. Remember that the *rotors* in (1.7) are *unique only up to real non-zero scalar factors*. For $g_1 = g_2$ the formula $R^2(\theta) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1}\mathbf{D}_2$, which rotates \mathbf{D}_1 by $+\theta$ into \mathbf{D}_2 would be sufficient. The opposite rotation would then be given by

$$R^2(-\theta) = \mathbf{D}_2^{-1}\mathbf{D}_1, \quad (\text{A1})$$

i.e. a rotation of \mathbf{D}_2 by $-\theta$ into \mathbf{D}_1 .

For $g_1 < g_2$ we need to replace the higher grade carrier \mathbf{D}_2 in (3.1) by the projection \mathbf{D}_1^p of the lower grade carrier \mathbf{D}_1 onto \mathbf{D}_2 , i.e. by

$$\mathbf{D}_1^p = (\mathbf{D}_1 \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_2^{-1})\mathbf{D}_2. \quad (\text{A2})$$

In this case we define

$$R^2(\theta) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1}\mathbf{D}_1^p = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1}(\mathbf{D}_1 \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_2^{-1})\mathbf{D}_2. \quad (\text{A3})$$

Due to the use of the left contraction, equation (A3) also returns a non-zero rotor $R^2(\theta)$ for $g_1 = g_2$ and $\mathbf{D}_1 \not\perp \mathbf{D}_2$. The right side of (A3) equals one, if $g_1 = 0$ or if $g_2 = 3$. The right side of (A3) is zero if and only if $g_1 > g_2$ or if $\mathbf{D}_1 \perp \mathbf{D}_2$.

For $g_1 > g_2$ we replace the higher grade carrier \mathbf{D}_1 in (A1) by the projection \mathbf{D}_2^p of the lower grade carrier \mathbf{D}_2 onto \mathbf{D}_1 , i.e. by

$$\mathbf{D}_2^p = (\mathbf{D}_2 \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_1^{-1})\mathbf{D}_1 = (\mathbf{D}_2 \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_1)\mathbf{D}_1^{-1}. \quad (\text{A4})$$

In this case we define

$$R^2(-\theta) = \mathbf{D}_2^{-1}\mathbf{D}_2^p = \mathbf{D}_2^{-1}(\mathbf{D}_2 \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_1)\mathbf{D}_1^{-1} = \mathbf{D}_2(\mathbf{D}_2^{-1} \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_1)\mathbf{D}_1^{-1}. \quad (\text{A5})$$

Reversion of (A5) also reverses the sign of the rotation angle θ

$$R^2(\theta) = \widetilde{R^2(-\theta)} = \widetilde{\mathbf{D}_1^{-1}}(\widetilde{\mathbf{D}_1} \lrcorner \widetilde{\mathbf{D}_2^{-1}})\widetilde{\mathbf{D}_2} = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1}(\mathbf{D}_1 \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_2^{-1})\mathbf{D}_2, \quad (\text{A6})$$

where the pairwise reversions of \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} and \mathbf{D}_1 (and of \mathbf{D}_2^{-1} and \mathbf{D}_2) produce equal sign changes, which cancel out. Due to the use of the right contraction, equation (A6) also returns a non-zero rotor $R^2(\theta)$ for $g_1 = g_2$ and $\mathbf{D}_1 \not\perp \mathbf{D}_2$. The right side of (A3) equals one, if $g_1 = 3$ or if $g_2 = 0$. The right side of (A6) is zero if and only if $g_1 < g_2$ or if $\mathbf{D}_1 \perp \mathbf{D}_2$.

For $g_1 = g_2$ we have $\mathbf{D}_1 \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_2^{-1} = \mathbf{D}_1 \llcorner \mathbf{D}_2^{-1} = \mathbf{D}_1 * \mathbf{D}_2^{-1}$, and equations (A3) and (A6) lead to identical rotors.

Adding equations (A3) and (A6) we get a general relative rotor $R(\theta)$ for all values of g_1 and g_2

$$R^2(\theta) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1}(\mathbf{D}_1 \lrcorner \mathbf{D}_2^{-1} + \mathbf{D}_1 \llcorner \mathbf{D}_2^{-1})\mathbf{D}_2. \quad (\text{A7})$$

The right side of (A7) equals two³ if $g_1 = g_2 = 0$ or if $g_1 = g_2 = 3$. It equals one if $g_1 \neq g_2$ and simultaneously $g_1 \in \{0, 3\}$ or $g_2 \in \{0, 3\}$. The right side of (A7) is zero if and only if $\mathbf{D}_1 \perp \mathbf{D}_2$, which was not the case for (3.1). But if the blades \mathbf{D}_1 and \mathbf{D}_2 are of the same grade $g_1 = g_2$, then a $\theta = \pi/2$ rotation from blade \mathbf{D}_1 onto \mathbf{D}_2 is well defined and unique. We take care of this exception by adding another rotation term

$$R^2(\theta) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} * \mathbf{D}_2 + \langle \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \times \mathbf{D}_2 \rangle_{\text{even}}. \quad (\text{A8})$$

Equation (A8) returns zero whenever $g_1 \neq g_2$. This can be easily checked out by inserting for \mathbf{D}_1 and \mathbf{D}_2 all possible combinations of scalars, vectors, bivectors, and trivectors. For $g_1 = g_2 = 0$ and for $g_1 = g_2 = 3$ equ. (A8) returns $R^2(\theta) = 1$, i.e. the identity transformation. But for $g_1 = g_2 = 1$ equ. (A8) produces the rotor

$$R^2(\theta) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{D}_2 + \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \wedge \mathbf{D}_2 = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \mathbf{D}_2, \quad (\text{A9})$$

and for $g_1 = g_2 = 2$ the rotor

$$R^2(\theta) = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} * \mathbf{D}_2 + \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \times \mathbf{D}_2 = \mathbf{D}_1^{-1} \mathbf{D}_2. \quad (\text{A10})$$

Finally the sum of (A7) and (A8) is zero if and only if both $g_1 \neq g_2$ and $\mathbf{D}_1 \perp \mathbf{D}_2$.

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³The cases $g_1 = g_2 = 0$, $g_1 = g_2 = 3$, and $g_1 \neq g_2$ with $g_1 \in \{0, 3\}$ or $g_2 \in \{0, 3\}$ result in $R^2(\theta) = 2$, and $R^2(\theta) = 1$, respectively. These values correspond to identity transformations. And indeed geometrically if at least one of the two objects under concern is a point or a sphere, then no relative rotation is required.

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